

Quantum Mechanics, Newton's Law, Cycling, Maximization of Probability

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In a series of notes, we argued that one could write the Schrodinger equation as:

$$\left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p \sin(px) \right] / \left[\sum_p f_p \sin(px) \right] + V(x) = E$$

Where f_p is a weight, $V(x)$ the potential and E energy. The $\sum_p f_p \sin(px)$, a normalization constant, can be called $W(x)$, the wavefunction. We also argued in another note that physically it seems that there is a resonance occurring with the potential described by $\exp(iEt)$, so the system is cycling over the f_p values. In a recent note, we argued that one could think of a quantum system in a potential as consisting of waves following the form $W(x) f_p \sin(px)$. This was described as $P(x \text{ intersection } p)$. In the literature, people have derived the Schrodinger equation from a variational principle by treating W^* and W as independent quantities. In this note, we wish to maximize $P(x \text{ intersection } p)$ subject to constant overall energy to obtain the Schrodinger equation. We try to argue that this is in the same spirit as maximizing entropy. We then note the connection to cycling and Newton's second law.

Conservation of Energy and Newton's Law

In (1), we argued that the Schrodinger equation could be obtained if one assumed that a particle with zitterbewegung, modeled by $\sin(px)$, was scattered into various momentum states by a potential $V(x)$. One also imposed energy conservation at each point x or:

$$\left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p \sin(px) \right] / \left[\sum_p f_p \sin(px) \right] + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

Here f_p is the momentum weight and $\left[\sum_p f_p \sin(px) \right]$ a normalization constant which is called the wavefunction. It should be noted that $W(x)$ is automatically the Fourier transform of f_p in this picture. One might argue that conservation of energy need not exist at each point x , but only overall. In other words one could write $E(x)$ such that $\int_x E(x) dx = E$. The form ((1)), however, preserves the idea of Newton's law, even for the ground state of quantum system.

Alternatively, one can write ((1)) in terms of energy densities which might be more physical. It is known that a quantum mechanical system will have a physical density $W(x)W(x)$ and according to classical physics $V(x)W(x)W(x)$.

$\frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{1}{2m} W(x)W(x) \right] + V(x)W(x)W(x) = E W(x)W(x) \quad ((2))$ where $\frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{1}{2m} W(x)W(x) \right]$ is the first term in ((1)).

One might argue that right hand side of ((2)) could be written as $E W(x)W(x) g(x)$ such that the integral over x of $E W(x)W(x) g(x)$ equals E . In such a case, $g(x)$ would need to have positive and negative values which would allow for its effects to cancel.

The fact that one does not use $E(x)$ or $g(x)$ shows that there is some underlying principle in quantum mechanics ruling out these solutions.

Momentum waves in a Potential

In (2), we argued that in quantum mechanics, one has momentum waves of the form $W(x) \sum_p \sin(px)$ with $W(x) = \sum_p \sin(px)$. Here $\sin(px)$ models the zitterbewegung motion of a particle, \sum_p is the momentum weight from scattering and $W(x)$ an space modifying amplitude due to the fact that normalization changes at each point x in (1). Thus, \sum_p and $W(x)$ are Fourier transforms of each other. If one sums over p one obtains $W(x)W(x)$ which is the spatial density. We argued in (2) that one could think of this wave as representing the probability of x intersection p :

$$P(x \text{ intersection } p) = W(x) \sum_p \sin(px) \quad ((3))$$

Consider ((3)) evaluated at x and $x + b$ where b is very small. Then:

Change in $\sum_p W(x) \sum_p \sin(px) = \text{Change in momentum flux} = [d/dx W(x)] W(x) + W(x) d/dx W(x) = d/dx [W(x)W(x)]$. This in turn can be written in terms of a momentum flux, namely $2 W(x) d/dx W(x)$. It is important to note the factor of 2 as there are contributions from a change in $W(x)$ and $\sin(px)$ as one moves from x to $x+b$.

In other words, the change in the momentum wave from x to $x+b$ equals the change in the spatial density $W(x)W(x)$.

Here $W(x) d/dx W(x)$ is the p momentum flux. It should be noted that the with the definition ((3)) describing a moving momentum wave which changes its amplitude as $W(x)$ one automatically obtains the "averaging" of quantum mechanics namely: $\text{Operator ave} = \langle W(x) | \text{Operator} | W(x) \rangle$.

Cycling

It was argued in (3), that the time-independent Schrodinger equation could be thought of in terms of cycling. In other words, one could think of the term $V(x) W(x)$ in terms of a product of two Fourier series, one for $V(x)$ and one for $W(x)$. In such a case:

$$\sum_p p^2/2m \sum_p \exp(ipx) + \sum_{k,j} V(k) \exp(ikx) \sum_j \exp(ijx) = E \sum_p \sum_p \exp(ipx)$$

Collecting terms in front of a particular $\exp(ipx)$ yields:

$$p^2/2m \psi + \sum_{k+j=p} V(k) f_j = E \psi$$

This suggests a kind of cycling equation with E representing the cycling frequency. $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ interact to create different momentum waves. These in turn interact again with $V(x)$ and so a resonance needs to be established. Thus, quantum mechanics does not need to simply be thought of in terms of averages ((1)), but can also be considered to be a cycling resonance. In terms of cycling, one needs to have a constant E on the right hand side of the equation. This defines the resonance which is occurring throughout space. It is this cycling behaviour which seems to rule out $E(x)$ or $g(x)$ described in earlier section.

The Schrodinger Equation from Variational Principles

The Schrodinger equation has been obtained from variational principles already a long time ago. The argument seems to be of the following nature. One has a wavefunction $W(x)$ and its complex conjugate $W^*(x)$. These are said to be independent because it seems that $W(x)$ can be written as $f(x) + i g(x)$. Next, one maximizes $\langle W | H | W \rangle + b \langle W | W \rangle$ subject to W^* where $\langle W | W \rangle$ is a constraint indicating that $W(x)$ is normalized to 1. Here H is the Hamiltonian which is Hermitian.

This approach is very interesting. For a bound system, however, $W(x)$ and $W^*(x)$, however, are the same. The full wavefunction is $\exp(iHt)W(x)$, but this does not seem to make the complex conjugate independent of $W(x)$. Furthermore, it is not clear what is the motivation of using a variational principle.

In statistical mechanics, one tries to maximize the entropy which is considered to be $-k$ times the logarithm of the number of states. Alternative derivations include $\sum P_n \ln(P_n)$ where P_n is a probability. From ((3)) we have a probability for p intersection x . We argue that this is very similar to the idea of entropy or the number of available states. We suggest maximizing ((3)) subject to the integral of energy density equaling E or energy. One might argue that the Schrodinger equation solutions determine what eigenenergies are allowed for a system and that experiment only shows differences between energy levels. Soft measurements, however, seem to allow one to measure spatial density and so one find $W(x)$, the wavefunction. One can then in principle calculate an energy density and integrate it. Let us attempt to maximize $P(x$ intersection $p)$

Maximize with respect to f_p 's where b is a Lagrange multiplier

$$W(x) \sum_p \sin(px) + b \int dx [W(x) \sum_p p^2/2m \sin(px) + V(x) W(x) W(x)]$$

This leads to an equation of the form:

$$[\delta W(x)] \sum_p \sin(px) + W(x) \sin(px) [\delta f_p] + b \{ [\delta W] \sum_p p^2/2m \sin(px) +$$

$$W(x) \sum_p p^2/2m \sin(px) [\delta f_p] + 2 W(x) V(x) [\delta W] \} = 0$$

Now $\delta W(x)$ can be thought of in terms of varying f_p so it seems that the above is equivalent to the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

Thus, it seems that one can obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation from a variational principle directly related to maximizing probability. This approach does not depend on W^* and W , but uses the relationship between f_p and $W(x)$, its Fourier transform and is motivated by the statistical mechanical idea of maximizing probabilities.

Comparisons and Conclusion

Thus, it is argued that the time-dependent Schrodinger equation can be thought of as arising from the maximization of $W(x) f_p \sin(px)$ which is a combination of three probabilities, $W(x)$ for space, f_p for momentum and $\sin(px)$ from zitterbewegung which causes interference, subject to energy conservation. This maximization, however, is equivalent to a cycling process which gives $\exp(iEt)$. In other words, it seems that one is arguing that a potential will scatter a zitterbewegung particle in a manner in which probability ($P(x \text{ intersection } p)$) can be maximized subject to an overall energy constraint. This cycling, however, depends on parameter E (energy) which is the frequency of cycling at any point in space. Thus, the idea of E exists at each point in space and makes ((1)) consistent with Newton's second law instead of leading to an $E(x)$ which only becomes E when average over space.

References

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